

Research Article

Legal Framework for Police Accountability in Nigeria- An Appraisal

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Abstract

Police accountability is a fundamental component of democratic governance and the rule of law, as it ensures that law enforcement agencies operate within the boundaries of legality, transparency, and respect for human rights. This paper views the legal framework for police accountability in Nigeria, providing a critical appraisal of the mechanisms designed to regulate the conduct and performance of the Nigeria Police Force. It reviews the current state of police accountability in Nigeria, identifying institutional, legal, and operational challenges that hinder effective oversight and responsible policing. Primary and secondary sources of data were used. These include constitutional provisions regarded as the grundnorm of the Nigerian legal system, statutory enactments governing policing, judicial decisions, scholarly textbooks, academic journals, and relevant online materials. Through an analytical examination of these sources, the paper explores the legal instruments and institutional arrangements that establish accountability within the police structure. Particular attention is given to both internal accountability mechanisms, such as disciplinary procedures and supervisory structures within the police organization, and external oversight mechanisms, including judicial review, legislative oversight, and civilian review bodies. The paper further assesses the challenges confronting effective police accountability in Nigeria, including institutional weaknesses, inadequate enforcement of disciplinary measures, corruption, political interference, and limited public confidence in law enforcement institutions. These challenges often undermine the effectiveness of existing accountability frameworks and weaken the capacity of the police to fulfill their constitutional mandate. Despite these limitations, the research highlights prospects for strengthening police accountability through legal reforms, improved oversight structures, enhanced transparency, and greater civic engagement. It is concluded that effective police accountability is essential for promoting public trust, safeguarding fundamental rights, and ensuring the proper functioning of the criminal justice system. It therefore recommends strengthening legal frameworks, improving institutional independence, and fostering a culture of professionalism and ethical conduct within the Nigeria Police Force.

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Introduction

Background of the Study

In Nigeria, prior to the advent of colonialisation, different communities that existed then had different kinds of arrangement for the maintenance of law and order while in some communities' religion played vital roles in the maintenance of such laws and orders. (for Nigeria, Age grades in other communities also carried out such roles akin to police duties today).¹ Also, oracles and supernatural forces played significant roles in the same vein. To restrain anti-social behaviour, the communities applied native restraints like social sanctions, public opinion, fears of retaliation, customary beliefs and other economic, moral, institutional pressures were used. in some areas, trial by ordeal were used to investigate crimes.²

The methods of maintaining law and order in our pre-colonial communities were virtually free and peaceful. ³ The Nigeria Police Force had its origin in Lagos between 1845 and 1861, it came into existence when the British officials serving in the Lagos territory during the second half of the 19th century encountered serious law enforcement problems resulting from their increased involvement in the "self-imposed" as to protecting the lives and properties of the indigenous people, the European merchants, other business and Christian Missionaries. British consul charged with the administration of Lagos colony whose numerous duties included the maintenance of law and order, that a consular Guard comprising three men was established in 1861.⁴

The modern police started as a consular guard of thirty (30) men in Lagos. In 1863, the guard became known as the "Hausa Police". The force was later recognized in 1879 by an Ordinance creating the constabulary of Lagos in 1894, the Niger constabulary of Lagos forced in Calabar. The Royal Niger Company formed another constabulary in Lokoja in

¹ A. B. Dambazau: "Criminology and criminal Justice" Chapter 5, P. 227

² Ibid, P. 229

³ The police in Modern Nigeria, 1861-1965, Ibadan, Ibadan University Press, pg. 90

⁴ Innocent Chukwuma, "Police transformation in Nigeria: Problems and Prospects, Ibadan, University Press, 1970 P. 129

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1888. Landmark development in the history of the Nigeria Police Force came in 1930, when the Northern and Southern Police were merged to form the Nigeria Police Force with Lagos as the force headquarters.

The 1999 Constitution also provides for the command structure and administration of the Police. The Nigeria Police as an institution under the 1999 Constitution is headed by the Inspector General of Police to be appointed by the President on the advice of the Nigeria Police Council from among the serving members of the Nigeria Police Force.⁵

The Constitution also provides for a Commissioner of Police for each State of the Federation who shall be appointed by the police Service Commission by virtue of the provisions of the Police Act made pursuant to *section 214(a)* of the 1999 Constitution, the structure of the Nigeria Police is fashioned along the Federal system in such a way the unit of command at the Federal, State and local levels is placed under a police officer in order of seniority.

The Nigeria Police command structure is divided into three categories of force Headquarters, Zonal Command and State Command. The Inspector General of Police is appointed by the President. Below the Inspector-General of Police (IGP) are six specialized offices of the Deputy Inspector-Generals (DIGs) in charge of different specialized departments. DIG 'A' Department is in charge of Financial and Administration of the Force. DIG 'B' Department is in charge of logistics and supply. DIG "D" Department is in charge of investigation and intelligence. DIG "F" Department is in charge of research and planning.

From the organization at the Force Headquarters, the force is further organized into twelve zones with each zone comprising of two to four state commands under the leadership of an Assistant Inspector General of Police who is answerable directly to the Inspector General of Police.⁶ In all the thirty-six states of the federation and the Federal capital, the command structure of the force is headed by a Commissioner of Police, followed by a Deputy Commission of Police in the day-to-day administration of the command.

⁵Section 215, CFRN, 1999

⁶2004Atidoga, D. F., The Nigeria Police, Human Rights Violation and Corruption: The Need for Reorientation, in *Journal of Contemporary Legal Issues*, Vol. 1. No. 1., Lagos, Sam Artrade Ltd, 2009, pg. 50-52.

The police and other law enforcement institutions are entrusted with a vast set of tasks demanding a high degree of probity within security sector as an organization and its oversight.⁷ Where this does not function well, law enforcement officers (police officers) may become vulnerable to acting unlawfully and outside their remit. To rescue the situation, police reform interventions are much needed. Reform can be in the form of retraining for police officers with a particular focus on human rights principles. In addition, a long-term effort is required to establish a functional framework for police oversight and accountability in order to strengthen accountability within the system of policing.

The Nigeria police force is constitutionally given the responsibility of maintaining internal security of the country. The constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria ⁸, in its *section 214* expressly provides for this responsibility state the provision here. Also, instructive is section 4 of the Police Act⁹, which is another source where the police derive its powers them equally contains this responsibility under *sections 4 and 27* respectively.

In enhancing police oversight and accountability, efforts must be one of the three key, related priorities. Firstly, where policing has been militarized and may be undemocratic and authoritarian, efforts must be made to enhance civilian control over the police. Secondly, it is necessary to increase public confidence in the police by upgrading the levels of police service delivery as well as by investigating and acting in cases of police misconduct.

While accountability is not restricted to dealing with complaints, an effective complaint system is to key to ensuring accountability. The police officers themselves are the key players in maintaining or restoring police accountability. The police accountability is not limited to the police and the independent police bodies. The various institutions that can be considered to constitute the state, each play a distinct role, not just as “clients” who need to be able to share their concerns, but also in sharing responsibility for fair and effective policing and accountability.

Police accountability, in particular, lies at the heart of security development. The term refers to more than ensuring that police services and its personnel uphold the law, respect human rights, and do not engage in misconduct, malfeasance, or corrupt behaviour.

⁷ Sections 214 and 215 CFRN, 1999

⁸ The 1999 CFRN

⁹ CAP P19 LFN, 2004.

Accountability also applies to ensuring that the policies of the police continually evolve toward greater congruence to current criminology best practices, such as in the use of force and firearms. Police accountability also means that the police's performance and responsiveness correspond to the priorities of the populace to whom the police deliver its service and is appropriately calibrated to meet the needs of different societal demographics¹⁰.

This paper aims to contribute to the growing body of knowledge on police accountability in Nigeria, Prospects and challenges. The research outcome, recommendations and conclusions will serve as practical tools for policy-makers and police seeking to enhance an effective police accountability system in Nigeria. The objective of this paper is to review the prospect and challenges of effective police accountability in Nigeria. It shall also consider the internal and external police accountability mechanism as well as suggest ways and means of achieving the required goal.

Prospects for an Effective Police Accountability Under a Democratic Dispensation

The expected prospects of an effective police accountability under a democratic regime in Nigeria lie in the mutual relationship between the police and the members of the public.¹¹ The Global Standards to combat ineffective police accountability, adopted by the International Criminal Police Organization (INTERPOL), aim to ensure that police have high standards of effective accountability and promote the development of “measure needed to prevent, detect, punish and eradicate corruption in the police within its national boundaries and to bring to justice police officers and other employees of police who are corrupt”.¹²

Noting that accountability and the oversight mechanisms for policing form the core of democratic governance and are crucial to enhancing rule of law and assisting in restoring

¹⁰ Organization for economic co-operation and Development, OECD, DAC Handbook on security system reform: supporting security and Justice, Paris, 2007. P.5.

¹¹ Tamuno, T.N. The police in modern Nigeria, 1861-1965, Ibadan University Press, P. 90

¹² Article 1. The general Assembly of INTERPOL adopted the Global Standards in 2002 by its resolution AG – 2002 – RES – 01 at its 71st session in Yaounde

public confidence in police, to developing a culture of human rights, transparency within the police and to promoting a good working relationship between the police and the public at large.¹³

In 2001, the Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe adopted the European Code of Police Ethics, which is the most elaborate such code in the world. The principles of the Code state that national laws relating to the police should accord with international standards to which the country is a party and must be clear and accessible to the public, and that the police should be subject to the same legislation as ordinary citizens. It contains the following provisions on accountability:¹⁴

- The police shall be accountable to the State, the citizens and their representatives.
- They shall be subject to efficient external control,
- Public authorities shall ensure effective and impartial procedures for complaints against the police;
- State control of the police shall be divided between the legislative, executive and the judicial power;
- Accountability mechanisms, based on communication and mutual understanding between the public and the police, shall be promoted,
- Codes of Ethics of the police, based on the principles set out in the Code; shall be developed in member states and overseen by appropriate bodies.

The Code also states that the police must be organized with a view to earning public respect, they must be under the responsibility of civilian authorities, they should normally be clearly recognizable; they should enjoy “sufficient operational independence” and should be accountable for the tasks carried out; police personnel at all levels should “be personally responsible and accountable for their own actions or omissions or for orders to subordinates; there should be a clear chain of command and “it should always be possible to determine which superior is ultimately responsible for the acts or omissions of police personnel, the police should be ready to give objective information on their activities to the public; the police organization should “contain efficient measures to ensure the accountability and proper performance of police staff, in particular to guarantee for individuals’ fundamental rights and freedoms; there should be effective measures to combat corruption; and disciplinary measures brought against

¹³ Democratic Oversight of police services: Mechanisms for Accountability and community policing NDI, 2005

¹⁴ Articles 59-63 of the European Convention for the prevention of Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment of people

police staff should be subject to review by an independent body or a court, and the public authorities should support police personnel who are subject to ill-founded accusations concerning their duties.¹⁵

Police Accountability: Best Practices

Democracy is a maximum standard for measuring certain system or type of government in any part of the world, Nigeria is no exception. The International Convention on Civil and Political Rights. ¹⁶set out principles on the fundamental rights of individuals to observe by States under democratic system of government.

The Code of Conduct for law Enforcement Officials, which refers to the various functions of law enforcement as well as different aspects of accountability as contained in the above-named Convention, states that the Code needs to be supported by additional important principles and prerequisites for the humane performance of law enforcement functions, namely:¹⁷

- (a) That every law enforcement agency, especially the police should be representative of and responsive and accountable to the community as a whole.
- (b) That the effective maintenance of ethical standards among law enforcement officials, depends on the existence of a well-conceived, popularly accepted and humane system of laws;

That every law enforcement agency, in fulfillment of the first promise of every profession, should be held to the duty of disciplining itself in complete conformity with the principles and standards herein provided and that the actions of law enforcement officials should be responsive to public scrutiny, whether exercised by a review board, a ministry, a citizen's committee or any combination thereof, or any other reviewing agency.

International standards also give directions to police officers in carrying out their duties and advising them on conduct to be avoided. They also enable both internal and external mechanism including individuals and groups, to monitor police actions with a view to enhancing democratic system. Transparency is a necessary part of accountability. It is about laws, policies, practices and circumstances of any limitations of the right to life as well as about the process and outcomes of necessary element in fulfilling the right to life.

¹⁵ Ibid

¹⁶ General Assembly Resolution 2200 A (XXI) annex

¹⁷ Ibid

For accountability to be effective, these should not be isolated clusters, but mutually complementing mechanisms. They are expected to cooperate with each other in good faith to ensure police accountability. For the police to strive to its functions under a democratic structure, the officers are to ensure that internal systems guarantee discipline, performance and all-round good policing. ¹⁸The police are hierarchical organization with a strict chain of command responsibility – the continuous oversight process, whereby superiors are to control their subordinates.

Independence Investigation into Police Misconduct

For police accountability to be fully effective, it must involve multiple actors and institutions performing multiple roles, to ensure that police operate in the public interest. It is crucial to have an institution overseeing the entire police accountability. Independent police oversight bodies (i.e. the police council, the police service commission “P.SC”, Police Community Relation Council (“PCRC”) and other bodies as they currently exist have different mandates. One focus on receiving, investigation and or recording complaints, another have general oversight functions, (over police performance in general, usually without focusing on specific cases); while others provide policy guidance for police deployment and personnel issues, usually, specifically focusing on the selection and appointment of the national head of the police (i.e. Inspector-General of Police).

For effective police accountability, there must be a fair and transparent appointment process for these bodies and its staff, which should be based on merit rather than on political or any other affiliation. Preferably, the heads of these bodies must be appointed for a fixed time period only, with a strict procedure for their removal.

Independence is best served if the appointments are made based on the ideal principle and staff carry out their functions with the highest degree of accountability and professionalism. Selecting the right staff or officers who meet the criteria of independence presents a particular challenge. Newly established independent bodies often have to do redeployment of police officers because of their unique experience in conducting investigations, which cannot be acquired otherwise. This was a similar situation with Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) when it was established. For effective police accountability, it is essential that independent bodies are mandated to

¹⁸ Ibid

deal with complaints against police officers.¹⁹ The following are the models used for oversight whose mandate are only to deal with complaints;

Investigation and quality assurance models: These share responsibility for investigations into allegations of misconduct with the police. They usually deal only with certain types of complaints and more serious complaints.

- i. **Review and appellate models:** After the police have completed an internal investigation into a complaint, the boards under this model review the file and decide whether a specific case was competently or fairly handled and, if not, request that the problem identified be corrected.
- ii. **Evaluative and Performance-based model:** These do not concentrate on individual complaints, but are geared to identifying patterns and practices of police misconduct and systemic failures to deal with them.
- iii. **Mixed model:** Oversight bodies may use a combination of two or more of the above models.

In principle, the independent body must investigate all deaths and serious injuries suffered while in police custody or as a result of police action; any use of lethal force (firearms) must always be investigated independently. It must be mandatory for the police to report these types of incidents to the independent bodies, and the investigation must commence immediately upon receipt of a complaint involving an allegation that could lead to criminal or disciplinary outcomes.²⁰

Independent bodies need to complement existing police accountability. It is safe to alter an existing structure to meet the criteria for independence. The best way to come about it, is an assessment of the strengths and weaknesses of the present system, the challenges it faces and their causes, to ensure that the new body or bodies is or are complementary.

The effectiveness of any accountability structure is dependent on visible and real political commitment on the part of both the executive and the parliament. The independent body or bodies should have sufficient funds to achieve its objectives²¹. Human resources are

¹⁹ A 2013 mid-term review of the Nigeria Justice for all (J4A) programme, October 18-November 1st, 2013. P. 5

²⁰ Tama Hopkins, An Effective system for investigating Rights compliance in Police complaint models in the USA, Canada, UK (Melbourne, Victorian Law Foundation, 2009).

²¹This notion is also reflected in Article 36 of the United Nations Convention against corruption. "such persons or staff of such body or bodies should have the appropriate training and resources to carry out the tasks..."

equally important. The management and leadership of the independent bodies is or are crucial factor in its success.²²

Four Dimensions of Accountability

Analysis of police accountability rarely refer to the broader literature on accountability in the belief that the police are a unique institution and that the value added of more generalized studies. It is a misguided perception, although every public institution and agency is unique, police accountability is a subject of the wider literature on accountability and good governance.²¹ This does not necessarily imply that what worked in advancing accountability in other governance arrears are readily transferable to police accountability, but only that there may be valuable lessons from which to draw inference(s).

More also, unlike police accountability, over the last decade empirical research has been conducted in development in other governance areas. The research has produced reliable and valid findings. From these findings, a plausible picture of how accountability can be strengthened in policing can be drawn.

For any public institution or agency, including the police, there are four possible dimensions along which accountability can be strengthened. These dimensions are not mutually exclusive and the first three fall under the “long route” to accountability category and, taken together, can also be labeled institutional capacity building. The fourth defines the “short route” and is under the purview of “social accountability”.

The four dimensions,²³with an illustrative list of the organizations and mechanisms of each in the context of policing, are as follows:

Horizontal Pertains to the Governance System of Checks and Balances: At the National and State levels, parliaments and ministries of finance and justice conduct horizontal checks on the police.²⁴ Other ministries may also exercise horizontal accountability on the police, such as ministries of women affairs and defence. Anti-

²² Miller, “Civilian Oversight of Policing: lessons from the literature, A Workshop series – A Role for Democratic policing (Washington, D. C. United States, Department of Justice, National Institute of Justice, 1997).

²³ This framework has been adopted, updated, and refined from DFID practice paper, Accountability Briefing Note. February, 2008.

²⁴ Cornwall et al, 2007, Isunza Vera 2006

Corruption offices as well as legal and organization, also conduct vital accountability functions and fall under this category. Also, federal auditors check and balance police performance too. The law and its provisions are an accountability mechanism and there may be a need to strengthen or tighten varying codes of procedure and other legal standards, ranging from public access to information, and intimate partner violence. The process by which citizens can sue police frequently is a key mechanism, as is the legislation concerning the establishment and organization of civil society, given their potential to function as an accountability mechanism on the police.

Comparative Analysis of Police Accountability

The history of police reforms generally in the sense of modern-day notions of police professionalization, is more than a century old²⁵. Over that time period there have been successive waves of reform movements with a changing set of objectives and programmes²⁶, and much has been accomplished to improve policing evidence of the reforms are especially significant in police management, crime fighting, tactics, police personnel standards and training, the diversity of the work force constitutional critical situations.²⁷

As policing concerns the institutionalized use of authority in the tasks of governing security, it requires governing in ways that hold those responsible accountable to democratic bodies. Accordingly, a key focus of policing debates has been on the institutional arrangement established for ensuring its structures of governance are democratically accountable.

Current Police Accountability in Nigeria

There is a long history of major police reforms that were considered important in their time that later faded away. During the colonial and post-colonial governments, the police was used for the maintenance of order in a way that engendered repression, culture of impunity, corruption, incivility, brutality, lack of transparency and accountability.²⁸

Also, the deplorable condition of the police continued during the 30 years of military rule in Nigeria from 1966 - 1999 excluding the civilian regime in between. There was acute

²⁵ Samuel Walker, *A Critical History of police Reform* ix (1977).

²⁶ Ibid.

²⁷ E. Alemika, "Police accountability institution and challenges in Nigeria, unreported manuscript, 2009.

²⁸ E. Alemika, "Police accountability institution and mechanisms in Nigeria, 2009.

underfunding, shortage of office and barracks accommodation, Meagre salaries and unpaid allowances were not paid. Above all, there was abuse of fundamental rights of citizens, while impunity was the order of the day for the above proposition, the following decided cases are instructive and to put the records straight.

In the case of *A.C.B. v. Okonkwo*,²⁹ the court through justice Niki Tobi, J.C.A. (as he then was) held on the issue of ineffective accountability

I know of no law which authorizes the police to arrest a mother for an offence committed or purportedly committed by the son. Criminal responsibility is personal and cannot be transferred. While I am aware of cases of vicarious liability in criminal law, the instant case is certainly not one. A police officer who arrests "A" for the offence committed by "B" should realize that he has acted against the law, such a police officer should, in addition to liability in civil action, be punished by the police authority. As a matter of fact, it bothers us so much for the police operating the law of arrest after three decades of Nigeria's independence, to arrest and detain innocent citizens of this country for offences committed by their relations. That is a most uncivilized conduct and one that any person with a democratic mind should thoroughly deter and condemn. I detest and condemn the uncouth practice.

Similarly, in the case of *Oludamilola v. The State*³⁰, the Supreme Court through Justice Niki Tobi, JSC (as he then was) held as follows on the issue of ineffective accountability.

This is a bizarre case of murder of an innocent citizen by a police officer. Visiting the police station is not an offence. Visiting the police station in sympathy with an arrested person is not also an offence. And also, the appellant had no right to shoot Solomon to death. There is evidence that the appellant was drunk at the time he shot the deceased. This brings to the fore the need to check police officers, immediately before and during duty, of drinking alcohol. I am sure that if the appellant was checked before he was posted to duty, there was the possibility of dropping him from the beat. In recent time, there are cases of drunken police officers shooting

²⁹ (1997) 1 NWLR (Pt. 480) 195, (Pages 207 – 208, Paras – H – B).

³⁰ (2010) 8 NWLR (Pt. 1197) 565 S.C. (Page 576: Paras, B – E).

innocent citizens to death. This is very serious and the Inspector-General of Police should do something about it.

The police therefore failed in its statutory responsibility to the citizenry and confidence was eroded³¹. The situation was further compounded by the military government assenting to needless proliferation of parallel security agencies in the country. These include the Economic and Financial Crime Commission; Independent Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Commission, Federal Road Safety Commission, Nigeria Security and Civil Defence Corps, National Drugs Law Enforcement Agency, etc.³² Consequently, the scarce resources that could have been used to strengthen the various organs of the Nigeria Police Force for effective accountability were expended in creating and sustaining these new agencies.

Since 1994, various attempts by governments were made to examine these problems with a view to reforming the Nigeria police force through the establishment of various panels and committees which made recommendations for reforms.³³

(i) **Effective implementation of policies for the Nigeria Police Force.**

A dedicated police reform office should be established and provided with all the necessary resources and facilities to guide and monitor the implementation of all the approved recommendations. The government should immediately produce a comprehensive National Police Reform Policy that clearly articulates and defines the role of the police accountability in the polity. The major objective of the policy will be to achieve functional responsibility for the force while enhancing its accountability and effective governance.

(ii) **Adequate Funding for the Police:**

The Nigeria police force should be well funded; be self-accounting and in total control of their budget as against the Ministry of Police Affairs controlling their budget. All police Zones, Commands and Formations should be involved in providing inputs into the budgetary process according to their needs.

(iii) **Decent Office and Residential Accommodation for Police Officers:**

New and modern police office complexes designed with security in mind should be built at the State, Division, Command and detachment levels. All dormitories in all the training colleges and institutions should be renovated and furnished with mattresses, pillows and adequate toilet facilities.

³¹ Cross Ref: the case of Oludamilola V. The state

³² The creation of various security agencies amount to duplication of duties

³³ M. D. Yusuf Panel to Reform and Reorganize the Nigeria Police Force, 1994.

(iv) **Effective Police Operation:**

The force intelligence should be revamped for better performance and the operatives should be spread across the country

- Intelligence gathering technology aids should be procured for the Nigeria police.
- A major police criminal data base should be set up at the National Level with links to State Commands and other government agencies responsible for the administration of criminal justice.
- The rules and regulations governing the deployment of police orderlies to eligible individuals as approved by Mr. President should strictly adhered to and any violation should be severely sanctioned.
- To ensure operational effectiveness, 85% of police personnel should be made up of operational agents, while 15% is made up of specialists and other supporting/auxiliary staff.
- There should be harmonious interaction between the Inspector-General of Police and the Police Service Commission.
- Enforcement of the various rules; such as, the Financial Regulations, the Police Force Regulations and Force Order. Others are the Police Service Commission Guidelines on Appointment, Promotion and Discipline in the Nigeria police force as well as the code of conduct for police officers on Election duties.

(v) **Discipline in the Police Force:**

A sound system of addressing police accountability to the people at every level should be established. The Police Service Commission, the Public Complaints Commission, and other Oversight Agencies should play a more proactive monitoring role over the police in order to improve the level of police accountability and public confidence.

(vi) **Adequate Training for the Police:**

The Police Service Commission should ensure that only those screened and adjudged suitable for training are recruited into the training colleges and or institutions.

(vii) **Promotion in the Force:**

The Police Service Commission should ensure the clearance of all backlogs of promotion in the force. Promotion should be an annual exercise for all deserving officers in accordance with the criteria adopted by the Police Service Commission. The IGP should establish promotion boards at the State and Zonal levels, staff training institutions and police colleges as well as formations to follow strictly the laid down procedures

The Challenges and Prospects of an Effective Police Accountability

In Nigeria, police officers are faced with various internal and external challenges. According to the first Indigenous Inspector-General of Police, Mr. L. O. Edet,

I am conscious of the weakness in the relationship between the force and the public they serve and it is my intention to do all in my power to improve this odd relationship...³⁴

To achieve this objective, the Nigeria police force established the Public Relations Department to help shore up the police image in 1964 but till date, not much has been achieved as members of the police still behave like occupational force and they perceive the public as their foes that have to be coerced, harassed and executed.³⁵

It is worthy of note that the adverse relationship that characterized the police and community in Nigeria is not entirely attributable to the police officers. The public lack adequate understanding of police functions and powers under the Constitution. As a result, lawful police acts are sometimes misunderstood and resisted and the police on their part do not tolerate anyone challenging their power and this will resort to force as well as violence to enforce it. A good example of these is the issue of Apo Village, FCT, a crisis between the police and the said villagers in 2008. This in most cases results in hostile police/community relationship.

One of the germane challenges militating against effective police accountability in Nigeria is political interference/control.³⁶ The 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria³⁷ vests the power of appointing the Inspector General of Police by the President on the advice of the Police Council. The president and other members of the police council (except the IGP) are all politicians.³⁸

By this provision, the President is given a wide range to choose whosoever he wishes because the constitution do not expressly provide for any qualification to be eligible for the appointment of the IGP except being a serving member of the Nigeria police force.³⁹ The politicians knowing the strategic nature of the office of the IGP and the enormous

³⁴ Ehindero, S. G., *Police and the Law in Nigeria*, Lagos, Time Press, 1986, page 123.

³⁵ Alemika, E. *Police accountability institutions and mechanisms in Nigeria*. Unpublished manuscript, 2009

³⁶ Section 215 (1) (a)

³⁷ Section 215(1) (a).

³⁸ 3rd Schedule of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria as amended.

³⁹ Ibid.

power wielded by the police, the President and members of the police council readily settle for a stooge or puppet that will obey their beck and call and do their bidding.⁴⁰

The constitution also empowers the President or Minister authorized in that behalf to give lawful direction to the IGP with respect to maintenance and security of public safety as well as public order as he may consider necessary and the IGP shall comply with those directions or cause them to be complied with immediate alacrity.⁴¹ Unfortunately, the constitution oust the court from enquiring into any direction so given.⁴²

In many instances, junior police officers are promoted and appointed into offices above and over their superiors.⁴³ The involvement of the political class in the promotion and posting of police officers enable them, (politicians) to use the police to oppress and suppress perceived oppositions. Until the above challenges are corrected much may not be expected from the police as the politicians have seized the police and its constitutional functions.

For an effective police accountability, it is interesting for members of the public to be able to file complaints against the erring police officer or officers. They should be in a better position to file a complaint against the police and indeed be facilitated in doing so, if they feel that they have been wrongly treated by the police. This is important because if there is no complaint, the police will miss a potential learning opportunity that could lead to an effective accountability.

A key to effective police accountability appears to be a series of facilitated dialogues, which bring together communities, police and other relevant stakeholders, to establish collaborative problem-solving relationships. This could be that of the communities, police, bar association, NGOs coming together at interval to discuss matters of importance that affect police accountability.

⁴⁰ Gibson KamauKuria, Harvard law school Cambridge Mass Chusset "The challenges posed by security

and state apparatus to the protection of human rights in Africa - yesterday, today and a vision of tomorrow by tunyi; Abayomi Esq. quoted by O.S Oyelade

⁴¹ Section 215(1)(3) of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria as amended.

⁴² Ibid (1) (5)

⁴³ Most of the promotions and postings are done on the basis of loyalty. The appointment of C. P Johnson was done by AlhajiAdedibu, the acclaimed politician, strongman of Ibadan politics, from a junior Deputy Commissioner of Police to Acting Commissioner of police over his senior and that of A.I.G. NuhuRibadu, the Pioneer Chairman of EFCC. (self analysis of the force).

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

This article examined the legal framework for police accountability in Nigeria with a view to assessing its effectiveness, identifying existing challenges, and highlighting possible prospects for improvement. Police accountability remains a critical component of democratic governance and the rule of law, particularly in a developing society where law enforcement agencies play a central role in maintaining public order and protecting citizens' rights. The Nigeria Police Force, being the primary institution responsible for internal security, is expected to operate within clearly defined legal and ethical boundaries. However, the findings of this study indicate that despite the existence of several legal and institutional mechanisms intended to regulate police conduct, the implementation and enforcement of these frameworks remain inadequate.

The article revealed that the Nigerian Constitution, statutory provisions, and other regulatory instruments provide the foundational legal basis for police accountability. These frameworks establish internal mechanisms such as disciplinary procedures and hierarchical supervision within the police institution, as well as external mechanisms including judicial oversight, legislative supervision, and public complaints procedures. Nevertheless, persistent challenges such as corruption, weak institutional enforcement, inadequate training, political interference, and lack of transparency have continued to undermine the effectiveness of these accountability structures.

Furthermore, the paper found that public trust in the police institution is significantly influenced by the level of accountability demonstrated by law enforcement officials. Where accountability mechanisms are weak or poorly enforced, incidents of abuse of power, misconduct, and human rights violations are more likely to occur, thereby eroding public confidence in the criminal justice system. Despite these challenges, the study also identified prospects for improving police accountability through stronger legal enforcement, institutional reforms, and enhanced public participation in oversight processes. Strengthening accountability within the police institution is therefore essential not only for improving policing standards but also for promoting justice, public confidence, and sustainable democratic governance in Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on this article, several recommendations are proposed to enhance effective police accountability in Nigeria.

First, there is a need for stronger enforcement of existing legal and institutional frameworks governing police conduct. Regulatory bodies responsible for oversight should be empowered to investigate allegations of misconduct independently and ensure that disciplinary measures are applied without bias or undue influence. Effective enforcement of existing laws will significantly improve compliance and professional conduct within the police force.

Second, institutional reforms should be introduced to strengthen both internal and external accountability mechanisms. Internal disciplinary structures within the Nigeria Police Force should be made more transparent and efficient, while external oversight bodies should be granted greater independence to perform their supervisory roles effectively.

Third, continuous professional training and ethical orientation for police officers should be prioritized. Such training should emphasize respect for human rights, professionalism, and adherence to the rule of law. Strengthening the ethical culture within the police institution will contribute to reducing incidents of misconduct and abuse of authority.

Fourth, mechanisms for public participation and complaints should be improved to ensure that citizens can report police misconduct without fear of intimidation or retaliation. Accessible and responsive complaint systems will help strengthen trust between the police and the communities they serve.

Finally, adequate funding and logistical support should be provided to enhance the operational capacity of oversight institutions and the police organization itself. Well-resourced institutions are better equipped to implement accountability mechanisms effectively and maintain professional standards.

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